

Optimising extraction of specific food allergens from challenging food matrices for immunoassay quantification – supplementary data

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S1. Preparation of allergen incurred foods

Ingredient screening

Ingredients used to prepare allergen-free matrices were chosen based on product labelling, e.g. no 'May Contain' labelling. Ingredients were confirmed to be allergen-free by immunoassay analysis. Materials were weighed out into new plastic-ware, and handled using disposable, single-use equipment. Mixing equipment was thoroughly cleaned with detergent prior to use.

Chocolate dessert

Chocolate dessert matrix was prepared according to Cochrane *et al* (1). See Table S01 for ingredients. Dry ingredients were combined in a stainless-steel mixing bowl and mixed for 5 minutes. Mixing was performed using a Metcalfe SP-200 Heavy Duty Planetary Mixer set to speed 1. Tween-60 emulsifier was dissolved into maize oil at 37°C, mixing at 125 rpm for 10 minutes. The oil-emulsifier mix was subsequently added to dry ingredients and mixed for 5 minutes. Water was gradually added to the resulting paste, during continuous mixing for 5 minutes. Material from the sides and bottom of the mixing bowl was manually incorporated and mixed for 10 minutes. Material was transferred to a plastic container and frozen at -20°C prior to the incorporation of allergen.

Table S01. Chocolate Dessert (CD) matrix ingredients.

CD ingredients	Supplier	Product details	Weight Used (g)
Cold swelling starch	Special Ingredients Ltd	ULTRATEX Instant thickener Batch K1135-0024	243
Cocoa	Dr. Oetker (UK) Ltd.	Fine Dark Cocoa Powder Batch L3179	413
Caster sugar	Silver Spoon, British Sugar plc	Caster Sugar Batch 3170FP	336
Maize Oil	Mazola (Edible Oils Ltd)	100% Pure corn oil Batch H3139	449
Tween 60	Merck Life Science UK Ltd	TWEEN 60 (Polysorbitan) #MKCP3449	11
Rice flour	Freee (Doves Farm Foods Ltd)	Freee Gluten Free Rice Flour #JC3201	45
Water	Welsh Water/Dwr Cymru Cardiff Supply	N/A	3500

Biscuit dough

Biscuit dough ingredients are outlined in Table S02. Initially, fats, sugars and flavourings were mixed for 10 minutes using a Metcalfe SP-200 Heavy Duty Planetary Mixer set to speed 1. Dry ingredients were subsequently added and mixed for an additional 10 minutes. Material from the sides and bottom of the mixing bowl was manually incorporated and mixed for 10 minutes. Material was transferred to a plastic container and frozen at -20°C prior to the incorporation of allergen.

Table S02. Biscuit matrix ingredients.

Biscuit ingredients	Supplier	Product details	Weight Used (g)
Gluten free rice flour	Freee (Doves Farm Foods Ltd)	Gluten free rice flour 1KG Batch JC3201	1931
Baking Powder	Asda Stores Ltd	Baking Powder 170g Batch 3177	19
Vegan butter	Stork, Upfield Europe BV	Vegan alternative baking spread 500g Batch L33261076	1448
Caster Sugar	Silver Spoon, British Sugar plc	Caster Sugar Batch 3170FP	965
Golden syrup	Lyle's Golden Syrup, ASR Grp	Lyle Golden Syrup Pouring Batch P3156238	483
Vanila extract	Waitrose Ltd	Cooks' Ingredients Madagascan Vanilla Extract 38mL Batch L3242	8

Allergen source materials and spiking mix preparation

Source materials covering egg, cow's milk, peanut, soy, cashew, walnut, almond, hazelnut, sesame, mustard, celery, crustacea and fish can be identified in Appendix A of manuscript and Table S03.

Source materials were quantified for total protein content by Kjeldahl analysis Crude (soluble and insoluble) UKAS accredited laboratory. The methods indirectly determine protein content through measurement of nitrogen. Nitrogen content was extrapolated to total protein content by multiplication of a 6.25x conversion factor.

Allergen-free matrices were used as a base to prepare allergen-incurred samples. A 1000ppm high dose was incurred initially, whereby the required amount of each source material required to prepare 1kg of incurred matrix at 1000ppm was calculated (e.g. 3067mg skimmed milk powder with 32.6% protein content = 1000mg protein in 1kg matrix). See Table S03 for calculated spiking values.

Source materials were weighed to prepare a 'source material mix' (SMM). Weighing for the SMM preparation was a critical step in matrix preparation and required the highest level of precision. Materials were weighed using an analytical balance, calibrated with 1mg, 100mg, 1000mg and 200000mg E2 certified calibration weights on the day of weighing. Source materials were weighed to within ± 1 mg of target value ($<0.1\%$). Source materials were weighed out onto Whatman low static weighing papers and combined in a polypropylene pot. The resulting source material mix was homogenised by vortex mixing at full speed for 2 minutes, placed on a roller mixer for 30 minutes at 60rpm and a final vortex for 2 minutes at full speed.

Table S03. Source material weights for incurring 1000ppm matrices. Total protein (K) determined by nitrogen content, Kjeldahl analysis, 6.25x conversion factor.

Sample	Supplier	Item	µg/g Total Protein (K)	Target Concentration (µg/g)	Target mass food (g)	Amount of source material required (mg)	% Ingredient in spike mix
Egg Powder	Sigma	egg powder EO500-1kg	801,000	1000	1000	1248.4	3.0
Milk Powder	Sigma	skimmed milk powder 70166-500g	326,000	1000	1000	3067.5	7.5
Peanut Flour	Golden Peanut Company	Light roast peanut flour 12% Fat	543,000	1000	1000	1841.6	4.5
Soy Flour	Sigma	Soybean flour Type 1S9633-500g	516,000	1000	1000	1938.0	4.7
Cashew flour	Beyond the nut	Organic (raw) cashew flour	212,000	1000	1000	4717.0	11.5
Walnut flour	Hortus Verdi	(Raw) Walnut protein flour	452,000	1000	1000	2212.4	5.4
Almond flour	Sukrin	Defatted (Raw) Almond flour	529,000	1000	1000	1890.4	4.6
Hazelnut flour	Bulgarian Nuts Premium	Hazelnut flour	165,000	1000	1000	6060.6	14.8
Sesame powder	Sukrin	Dehusked and defatted (raw) sesame seed flour	454,000	1000	1000	2202.6	5.4
Mustard powder*	Colmans	Colmans Mustard Powder, double superfine	287,000	1000	1000	3484.3	8.5
Celeriac powder	Vehgro	Celeriac ground organic powder	108,000	1000	1000	9259.3	22.6
Shrimp Powder	Baracel	Shrimp powder 37411	648,000	1000	1000	1543.2	3.8
Salmon Powder*	AABaits	Salmon fishmeal	680,000	1000	1000	1470.6	3.6

*Note: mustard and salmon source materials included in mix. Specific allergens from these were not analysed in the present study due to assay redevelopment.

1000ppm, 100ppm and 10ppm incurred matrix preparation

To form the 1000ppm matrices, approximately 500g of placebo matrix that had been defrosted and brought to room temperature was added to a stainless-steel mixing bowl, and allergen SMM carefully added on top. Additional placebo matrix was added to bring the total weight in the mixing bowl to 1000g. The matrix was homogenised using a Russell Hobbs GoCreate stand mixer on the lowest speed setting '1'. Matrix was mixed for 10 minutes, followed by manual incorporation of material from the side of the bowl and paddle mixer. This was repeated an additional 5 times to give a total of 1 hour mixing. 100ppm and 10ppm matrices were prepared by dilution of the 1000ppm or 100ppm 1-in-10 in placebo matrix (100g of 1000ppm to 900g placebo) and homogenised as previously described.

Baked biscuit preparation

Biscuit dough (placebo, 10, 100 and 1000ppm incurred) was chilled to 4°C, 40g portions were weighed out and rolled into spheres, stored at 4°C prior to baking. Biscuits were baked in a MONO DX DECK OVEN. Biscuits subjected to standard cooking were baked under recommendation by the Head of Baking at the ZERO2FIVE food industry centre, Cardiff, Wales, to model how a biscuit of this type would be cooked in a real-life scenario and therefore reflect how the item would be consumed. These conditions were 185°C for 15 minutes, where all biscuits were cooked on a single oven shelf.

Baked biscuits were homogenised by combining several biscuits within a single use Ziploc bag and crushing. The resulting crushed biscuits were ground using a Aigostar 300105KYI coffee grinder. Sample was ground on full speed for 30 seconds. Any material present on the sides or bound in large particles was distributed using a disposable spatula. This process was repeated a further 4 times for a total of 5 mixes.

S2. Calculation of incurred matrix recovery example calculation

Foods were incurred to 10ppm, 100ppm, and 1000ppm based on total protein determined by Kjeldahl using the standard nitrogen conversion factor of 6.25.

1. Almond flour quantified by immunoassay to contain 219,508 microgram of Pru du 6 per gram of almond flour ($\mu\text{g/g}$, equivalent to parts per million [ppm]).
2. Almond flour was previously determined to contain 529,000 microgram of protein per gram of almond flour by Kjeldahl analysis.
3. Calculate specific allergen:total protein ratio
 - a. almond flour contains 219,508 μg of Pru du 6 per 529,000 μg of total protein.
 - b. 1 μg almond protein contains 0.415 μg Pru du 6
 - c. Therefore, at defined levels of total protein:
 - i. 1000ppm almond protein = 415 $\mu\text{g/g}$ Pru du 6.
4. Incurred foods analysed by immunoassay to determine specific allergen content:
1000ppm chocolate dessert contains 425 $\mu\text{g/g}$ Pru du 6
5. Calculate recovery (observed/expected)*100: ((425 $\mu\text{g/g}$ / 415 $\mu\text{g/g}$)*100) = **103%**

Recovery

S3. Api g 1 extraction temperature assessment.

Source material mix and 1000ppm incurred matrices were extracted in PBS, 2% Tween-20, 1M NaCl, pH 7.4 in a 1:10 sample ratio (e.g. 1g sample: 10mL extraction buffer), vortex mixed for 30 seconds to suspend material and incubated at either 37°C or 60°C for 15 minutes, shaking at 175rpm. Results are shown in Table S04.

Supplementary Table S04. Extraction temperature assessment for Api g 1. Results are average of n=2, or n=3^o replicate extractions and reported as microgram of Api g 1 per gram of food ($\mu\text{g/g}$).

	Api g 1 ($\mu\text{g/g}$)		
	37°C	60°C	% Difference
Source material spike mix	72	32	-77
1000ppm Biscuit Dough	1.78	2.64 ^o	39
1000ppm Baked Biscuit	0.011	0.009 ^o	-20
1000ppm Chocolate Dessert	2.69	2.41 ^o	-11

Supplementary Table S05. Specific allergen measurements using optimised extraction buffers. Results reported as microgram per gram of food ($\mu\text{g/g}$). Spiking mix measured for $\mu\text{g/g}$ specific allergen content[†], multiplied up to expected specific allergen content in whole source material^{††} depending on % composition in spike mix (See table S03 for composition). Source material total protein content determined by Kjeldahl ($\mu\text{g/g}$)[nitrogen content $\times 6.25$][‡] used to calculate expected target value[§] of specific allergen content at defined levels of total protein.

		Specific allergen content ($\mu\text{g/g}$)													
Matrix	Extraction buffer:	Egg		Peanut		Cow's Milk			Tree nuts			Sesame	Shrimp	Celery	Soy
		Gal d 1	Gal d 2	Ara h 3	Ara h 6	Bos d 5	Bos d 11	Pru du 6	Ana o 3	Jug r 1	Cor a 9	Ses i 1	TPM	Api g 1	Gly m 5
		J	J	D/J*	D/J*	J	D	J	J	J	J	J	D	J	J
Source Material	Spiking mix [†]	1383	11794	772	213	701	7504	10137	2485	478	12883	1188	46	75	2636
	Source material ^{††}	45359	386721	17166	4745	9357	100139	219508	21564	8841	87019	22081	1212	330	55675
	Source total protein [‡]	801000 [‡]		543000 [‡]		326000 [‡]		529000 [‡]	212000 [‡]	452000 [‡]	165000 [‡]	454000 [‡]	648000 [‡]	108000 [‡]	516000 [‡]
Expected Target Value [§]	10ppm	0.57	4.8	0.32	0.087	0.29	3.1	4.1	1.0	0.20	5.3	0.49	0.019	0.031	1.1
	100ppm	5.7	48	3.2	0.87	2.9	31	41	10	2.0	53	4.9	0.19	0.31	11
	1000ppm	57	483	32	8.7	29	307	415	102	20	527	49	1.9	3.1	108
Biscuit Dough	0ppm	<0.3125	<0.002	<0.0048	<0.0004	<0.002	<0.002	0.012	<0.0008	<0.0008	<0.020	<0.001	<0.002	<0.0312	<0.078
	10ppm	0.46	4.4	0.28/0.39	0.080/0.081	0.25	2.4	4.3	1.1	0.23	5.0	0.47	0.006	<0.0312	0.74
	100ppm	3.8	45	4.3/4.5	0.92/0.95	2.0	34	39	11	2.0	64	4.2	0.17	0.16	10
	1000ppm	39	385	37/36	7.2/7.2	26	292	426	98	21	741	43	1.6	2.6	113
Baked Biscuit	0ppm	<0.3125	<0.002	<0.0048	<0.0004	<0.002	<0.002	0.007	<0.0008	<0.0008	<0.020	<0.001	<0.002	<0.0312	<0.078
	10ppm	<0.3125	0.003	0.23/0.35	0.056/0.043	0.003	0.86	2.6	0.33	0.10	3.2	0.27	<0.002	<0.0312	<0.078
	100ppm	<0.3125	0.074	1.6/2.4	0.42/0.39	0.030	7.4	20	2.9	1.3	46	2.2	0.010	<0.0078	1.9
	1000ppm	0.97	11	23/28	5.0/4.8	3.5	218	264	46	16	396	24	0.33	0.009	32
Chocolate Dessert	0ppm	<0.3125	<0.002	<0.0048	<0.0004	<0.002	<0.002	<0.0048	<0.0008	<0.0008	<0.020	<0.001	<0.002	<0.0312	<0.078
	10ppm	0.29	3.6	0.20	0.041/0.060	0.15	1.5	3.0	0.95	0.20	3.8	0.43	0.003	<0.0312	0.13
	100ppm	3.3	40	1.7	0.56/0.46	1.3	11	21	6.5	1.6	42	3.9	0.12	0.17	1.5
	1000ppm	34	321	22	5.1/4.3	16	226	270	72	19	511	31	1.7	2.4	42

Supplementary Table S06. Lowest level of detectable allergen relative to method limit of detection (LOD). Unless otherwise specified results are from 10ppm incurred samples. *Denotes 100ppm samples, **denotes 1000ppm sample.

Allergen	Specific Allergen	LOD (µg/g)	Biscuit Dough		Chocolate Dessert		Baked Biscuit	
			Allergen Content (µg/g)	Fold higher	Allergen Content (µg/g)	Fold higher	Allergen Content (µg/g)	Fold higher
Almond	Pru du 6	0.0024	4.30	1792	2.96	1233	2.62	1090
Walnut	Jug r 1	0.0004	0.23	577	0.20	492	0.10	251
Hazelnut	Cor a 9	0.0078	5.02	644	3.84	492	3.20	411
Cashew	Ana o 3	0.0004	1.09	2736	0.95	2365	0.33	819
Sesame	Ses i 1	0.0010	0.47	469	0.43	430	0.27	268
Peanut	Ara h 3	0.0024	0.39	163	0.13	54	0.35	144
	Ara h 6	0.0002	0.08	406	0.06	299	0.04	217
Egg	Gal d 1	0.1563	0.46	3	0.29	2	0.97**	6
	Gal d 2	0.0010	4.36	4363	3.59	3588	0.00	3
Cow's milk	Bos d 5	0.0010	0.25	252	0.15	149	0.00	3
	Bos d 11	0.0010	2.39	2390	1.52	1516	0.86	856
Soy	Gly m 5	0.0781	0.08	10	0.02	2	0.12*	15
Celery	Api g 1	0.0039	0.16*	2	0.17**	2	0.01**	426
Shrimp	STM	0.0010	0.01	6	0.01	3	0.003*	10

References:

1. Cochrane SA, Salt Lj Fau - Wantling E, Wantling E Fau - Rogers A, Rogers A Fau - Coutts J, Coutts J Fau - Ballmer-Weber BK, Ballmer-Weber Bk Fau - Fritsche P, et al. Development of a standardized low-dose double-blind placebo-controlled challenge vehicle for the EuroPrevall project. *Allergy*. 2012;67(1):107-13. doi: 10.1111/j.1398-9995.2011.02715.x.